

BUSINESS ETIQUETTE, FORMAL AND INFORMAL SPEAKING METHODS

Saydamatova Nigora Sheralievna
Tashkent State Agrarian University
nigorasaydamatova134@gmail.com
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7785285>

Abstract This article discusses the methodology of communication at the meeting. In formal dialogues, body movements and sound tenders are given with examples.

Key words: meetings, communication, Body Language, discussion, essential tip, business leadership.

Аннотация В данной статье рассматривается методология коммуникации на встрече. неформальные диалоги, телодвижения и звуковые сигналы сопровождаются примерами.

Ключевые слова: встречи, общение, язык тела, дискуссия, важный совет, деловое лидерство.

A big part of learning how to run effective meetings is related to communication, so a strong emphasis must be placed on this area. Learning to communicate better in meetings can boost overall business results because they become more productive and are more likely to achieve objectives.

Understanding how to run effective meetings is a major part of successful business leadership, and communication plays a crucial role in this. If you can get ideas across clearly, keep people's attention, make effective use of body language and steer conversations in the right direction, your meetings will become much more successful. Delivering better meetings is important because many business gatherings lack focus and fail to achieve what they were supposed to. In this article, we provide five specific tips so that you can communicate better in meetings.

It is no exaggeration to say that the success or failure of business meetings will hinge on the effectiveness of your communication, as well as the communication skills of the other attendees. You need to make sure you are speaking clearly and are getting your points across in a way that can be easily understood by everyone else.

Another major point to understand is that communication is not one-directional. You can be a good orator, delivering good content, but if you are not a good listener, your overall ability to communicate effectively will suffer.

With the increasing importance of video meetings, reinforced by the COVID-19 pandemic, adopting good communication habits has become even more vital. When videoconferencing, the speaking time has to be used efficiently and needs to be respected by everyone. Even a small interruption can lead to a loss of attention or a waste of precious minutes when one takes into account the lags caused by bad connections.

One of the best ways to improve your communication is to record your meetings and listen to them back. While many people dislike the experience of listening to themselves, it is the best way to pick up on what you do well and where you need to make improvements. Of

course, there are also some top tips to be aware of too. Although it is vital to organize your thoughts and say the right things, the actual effectiveness of your communication within meetings can potentially be enhanced by intelligent use of relevant technology.

Especially in circumstances where meetings involve participants in various locations and time zones, it is essential to have devices and software that will support remote and hybrid meetings. For instance, an interactive display can help provide visual information and multimedia content for clearer communication. Supported with the my ViewBoard ecosystem that is compatible with software solutions like Zoom, you can communicate to remote participants much more effectively.

Should you be having the meeting from home, it will be wise to invest in a good-quality monitor that enhances communication from afar. Some monitors feature ergonomic capabilities that allow you to stand to present even in the comforts of your own home. USB-C monitors can also streamline how you share and present content, making sure that the participants in the meeting can easily view the information quickly and easily.

Pay Close Attention to Your Body Language

When people think about communication, they immediately think about speech or written communication. However, a significant part of the way we communicate with other people occurs through body language. Therefore, to communicate better in meetings, you need to pay close attention to yours.

As an article from Forbes on body language in leadership points out, people make snap judgments based on your body language. Before a meeting, you need to consciously think about how you sit or stand. Avoid closed body language, such as crossed arms, and try to make plenty of eye contact with other people in the meeting, and adopt a good posture. While it may not always be possible or appropriate, meetings tend to work better when the attendees are involved in a conversation rather than simply listening to a long speech. However, some of those attending the meeting may be reluctant to interject or to volunteer points themselves, which is why questions are so important.

Ideally, you should try to make intelligent use of questions to push the conversation forward and to get specific ideas from people. Questions can be aimed at the group, with attendees being given a chance to volunteer an answer, or aimed at individuals, which can be a good way to keep people engaged.

Finally, another essential tip for improving the quality of communication in meetings is to keep unnecessary distractions to an absolute minimum. On a basic level, you need to ensure the room is soundproofed or located far enough away from unwanted background noise, but there is also a need to eliminate distractions inside the room too.

In an article in Inc. Magazine, 80% of workers understand mobile phones can be a distraction in meetings. However, about 50% still use them anyway. You can politely remind all meeting attendees to keep their mobile phones or laptops away so that they can pay attention to the messages conveyed during the meeting.

Restrict the number of devices in the meeting to those that are needed. If attendees do not require laptops to contribute to the meeting, avoid having them on desks. Paper handouts may be needed, but you need to avoid situations where people are caught between listening to the discussion and reading the content. Communication is a critical component of understanding how to run effective meetings, and learning to communicate better can easily

be the difference between an unproductive meeting that wastes everybody's time and a good one that delivers on the original objectives.

What you say must have a purpose, and you need to stay on topic. However, you must remember that communication does not only go one way, and it is also not only about what you say. Bring others into the discussion and pay attention to your body language. Make effective use of technology and eradicate unnecessary distractions.

Recording meetings and listening to them back is a great way to pick up on areas of strength and areas of weakness. As you improve your communication, the overall quality of your business meetings will inevitably improve too.

To learn about the types of meetings to be having for better company welfare and improved productivity, you can read our handy guide here. Or you can browse ViewSonic's meeting devices and solutions for more effective communication in meetings.

References:

- 1.<https://www.viewsonic.com/library/business/5-ways-to-communicate-better-in-meetings/>;
- 2.Entrepreneur Media, Inc. "The Right Way to Network on Social Media." Entrepreneur. Entrepreneur, 19 February 2015. Web. 9 May 2018;
- 3.Misner, Ivan. "What Is Business Networking, Anyway?" Entrepreneur. Entrepreneur, 29 August 2008. Web. 9 May 2018;
- 4.Misner, Ivan. "The 5 Types of Business Networking Organizations." Entrepreneur. Entrepreneur, 1 November 2017. Web. 9 May 2018.
- 5.Schweitzer, Sharon. "The Importance and Value of Business Networking." The Huffington Post. TheHuffingtonPost.com, 3 August 2017. Web. 9 May 2018;
- 6.Rizk, Elias. "How to improve your sales performance at networking events? Archived 9 December 2019 at the Wayback Machine" ebCard, 12 November 2019.

